

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14434747>

THE MAKING OF NICKNAMES AND PSEUDONYM THROUGH WORD- MAKING TOOLS

Obidova Azizaxon Davronboy qizi,

Farg‘ona davlat universiteti doktoranti

E-mail address: obidovaaziza61@gmail.com

***Abstract:** This chapter talks about the semantic properties of the nicknames and nicknames under study, the process of making words and phonetic means. It also highlights word formation models within words; clarifies the structural types of complex nicknames and nicknames as well as, the types generated by abbreviations.*

***Key words:** Pragmatic, semantic, structural, phonetic, word-formation, "emotional", "emotive", "expressive", "affective", "emotionally expressive.*

TAXALLUS VA LAQABLARNING SO‘Z YASASH VOSITALARI ORQALI YASALISHI

***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu bobda o‘rganilayotgan laqab va taxalluslarning semantic xususiyatlari, so‘z bo‘lib yasash jarayoni va fonetik vositalarini haqida so‘z boradi. Shuningdek, so‘z tarkibidagi so‘zlarni shakllantirish modellarini yoritib; murakkab laqab va taxalluslarning tarkibiy turlarini hamda, qisqartirish orqali hosil qilingan turlarini aniqlashtirib beradi.*

***Kalit so‘zlar:** Pragmatik, semantik, tarkibiy, fonetik, so‘z shakllanishi, "hissiy", "hissiy", "ekspressiv", "affektiv", "hissiy ekspressiv.*

СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОЗВИЩ И КЛИЧЕК С ПОМОЩЬЮ СЛОВООБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ

Аннотация: В этой главе рассматриваются семантические особенности изучаемых прозвищ и прозвищ, процесс словообразования и фонетические средства. Также освещаются модели словообразования в словосочетании; уточняются структурные типы сложных прозвищ и прозвищ, а также типы, образованные сокращениями.

Ключевые слова: прагматический, семантический, структурный, фонетический, словообразовательный, "эмоциональный", "эмотивный", "экспрессивный", "аффективный", "эмоционально экспрессивный."

Up to this point, lexical and semantic means of secondary nomination formation have been analyzed. But the emergence of new meanings in the language is related not only to semantic shifts and semantic transformations in existing ready-made units, but also semantic shifts in word formation. The act of nominating a word-forming character necessarily involves the use of a certain formal operation or formal means, the choice of which is subordinated to the semantic task of this act [Kubryakova, 1977: 238]. Word formation is directly related to secondary nomination, since it is an extensive area of modeling of special units of nomination – derivatives. As E.S. Kubryakova notes, a derived word is any secondary, that is, a unit of nomination conditioned by another sign or a set of signs with the status of a word, regardless of the structural simplicity or complexity of the latter. E.S. Kubryakova refers to derivatives of affixal type, complex words, and derivatives created by conversion or truncation [Kubryakova, 1965: 23-24]. Therefore, it is important to analyze the relations of word-formation derivation and establish models of their occurrence. Indeed, the specificity of the derivative, as a completely unique unit of the language system, can be realized only when referring to the process as a result of which it is born, formed and formed. One more circumstance should be

pointed out, emphasizing the important role of word formation for the secondary nomination. The existence of certain traditions in this area in the language and, most importantly, the existence of productive and long-standing word-formation models approved by society in the language leaves its imprint not only on how exactly the new phenomenon is called, but also on its very fixation in the human mind [Kubryakova, 19977: 236]. In other words, the existence of certain word-formation models facilitates the choice of what should receive a separate name in the surrounding reality. Undoubtedly, a person himself, proceeding primarily from practical needs and social experience, determines what is to be called and what should be called by language. But an integral feature of this experience is also knowledge of the language, and, in particular, word-formation models. Focusing on the structure of the model, its composition and the arrangement of its components in it, a person can easily guess the meaning of a derived word, i.e. a secondary name. Thus, onomasiological (or conceptual) categories, which form the basis of naming in any language, are realized at the level of a derived word with the help of specific formal means. The main onomasiological categories of language, according to A.A. Ufimtseva, E.S. Aznaurova, E.S. Kubryakova, V.N. Telii, are those thanks to which words are formed as words of different formal classes and as signs of different nature (proper names, or full-valued parts of speech, as opposed to quantifiers, formators, etc., that is, non-significant parts of speech, as well as pronouns and numerals) [A.A. Ufimtseva, E.S. Aznaurova, E.S. Kubryakova, V.N. Telia, 1977: 56].

In turn, onomasiological categories that implement proper names can be considered the category of substance (or the category of objectivity) and the category of attribute. The category of substance is reflected in grammar in the form of such a part of speech as a noun. The category of the attribute covers three other significant parts of speech - verb, adjective, adverb. The values expressed by these parts of speech can be considered the most abstract general categorical values. Perhaps the most productive word-forming way of forming a nickname vocabulary is affixation,

i.e. the creation of new words by attaching certain word-forming elements - affixes to the basis. In our case, we are dealing with suffixes. It is known that word-forming suffixes have lexical and lexico-grammatical meanings. The lexical meaning of a suffix means its ability to change the lexical meaning of the whole it forms. The lexical and grammatical meaning of a suffix is defined as its ability to carry out such a semantic and morphological restructuring of the word being formed, which changes its attribution to one or another part of speech. The lexical meaning of this suffix has an agentive character, i.e. it denotes a figure or just an animated person. There is no specific type of evaluation assigned to this suffix. The assessment is created due to the semantics of the motivating basis and the evaluative attitude of the speaker to the referent. The basis contains a feature that serves as the base of the secondary name. On the basis of this feature, there is a metaphorical or metonymic rethinking of the meaning of the word. In general, expressiveness, emotionality and evaluativeness are achieved due to metaphor, metonymy and suffixation.

REFERENCES:

1. Галкина-Федорук Е.М. Об экспрессивности и эмоциональности в языке/Е.М. Галкина-Федорук // Профессору Московского университета акад. В.В. Виноградову / МГУ им. М.В. Ломоносова: Сб. статей по языкознанию. -М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1958. - С. 16-30.
2. Гальперин И.Р. Очерки по стилистике английского языка / И.Р. Гальперин. - М.: Изд-во лит. на иностр. яз., 1958. - 443 с.
3. Никитин М.В. Курс лингвистической семантики / М.В. Никитин. - СПб.: Науч. центр пробл. диалога, 1996. - 753 с.
4. Никитин М.В. Основы лингвистической теории значения / М.В. Никитин. - М.: Высш. шк., 1998. - 160 с.
5. Никитин М.В. Метафорический потенциал слова и его реализация / М.В. Никитин // *Studia Linguistics* Вып. 10. Проблемы теории европейских

- языков. - СПб.: Изд-во РГПУ им А.И. Герцена, 2001. - С. 37-43.
6. Ретунская Е.М. Английская аксиологическая лексика / Е.М. Ретунская; науч. ред. В.А. Хомяков. - Н. Новгород: Изд-во ННГУ, 1996. - 250 с.
7. Galperin I.R. Stylistics / I.R. Galperin. - M.: Higher school publ. house, 1971. - 332p.
8. Ball A.M. Compounding in English Language / A.M. Ball. - N.Y.: The H.W. Wilson Co., 1941.-207 p.
9. Black M. Models and Metaphors / M. Black. - Ithaca, N.Y.: Cornell Univ. Press, 1962. -267 p.
10. Collins Russian English English Russian dictionary / A. Ozieva, O. Stott, M. Hepburn. - Glasgow; N. Y.: Harper Collins Publ., 1996. - 564 p.